

GARBLED LINES

Amonova Marjona

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages

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If you want to know all of them, close your eyes...

"Aspiration which prompts you to this story is me. Yes, of course. It's me! In order to read this story, you have to be interested in me. If you ignore this statement, close this page, do not read it. If this is trust, good! Keep going. Close your eyes and daydream about me a little bit.

Do you want to improve yourself? Firstly, you should throw your pride under your feet. When it settled there, undoubtedly pride can lift upwards you. Pride. What do you think...Do I have got it? If I am not a mistake, I have an idiocy and fantasist. As you know, currently I am playing silly buggers because at the moment it is time to pray for Allah in Muslim community. What am I doing this time...Just I am daydreaming. I am decorating the paper with a pencil in my hand. At the moment, I am daydreaming. " I am very rich woman and a girl who achieved people's respect. I am selfish who want to be one of the rich people . You know what, I desire to give a pair of tickets for Haj to my parents. But I am not betrayer, I do not have a traitorous behavior.

I fought with envy and I won.

As a result, for reward I learnt to admire.

It is trust.

Somehow, I am a winner because admiring is my friend. It always be with me. Envy left from me at the age of 19 or 18. I hope that it did not have in my life. I have admired when I saw red-coloured automobile which was glittering as fire called "MALIBU" and a woman who handled this car. I admired when I saw clever girls who tend to wear as elegant way at my university. I admired when I saw expatriate students who visited to study in our country or other countries. All of them are pure admiration and sincere looks. Could you imagine how I am flattered by this attitude?!

My soul wants love

I can not love Allah. I desire deeply to love Allah

If you know, you really love Allah...come on, teach me!!!

Right, at this my age I do not constantly pray on time. But from this, spine grows up in my heart every moment. I tend to be sorrowful from thinking about this every time. Nevertheless, I am not still too. Sometimes, when I see people who wear a hijab, I flourish as sunflower from happiness. My admiration

bubbles up while I want to become like them. Their outer worlds are pretty as their inner worlds. They make my heart boil from kindness. They can ventilate their love to Allah in five times in per day.

Right, till this period I have not prayed. I have caused to pass away my namaz. However, they never slip my mind in a sec. I know that my knowledge about our religious is low. Though, I desire to know all of them. I need you who know about these. You love Allah, do not you? You teach me slowly and one by one. You help me to go towards Allah.

Not only those who have experienced it, but also those who observe the surroundings are masters of high-flown words.

If someone have the ability to observation, s/he can give own summary for something, even though it happens or does not happen in her/his destiny. As I said, it depends on the ability of observation. However a person who lived in a particular situation, speak with sensation unlike observant people. Let's imagine, someone make a cocktail with the help of combining all conclusions, which realize past events, and feelings in that occasion. Than s/he presents it to you. After tasting, you just try to praise her or his skill with grandiloquent languages. Is it so..? Is it true for you..?

Grandiloquent languages, why does it need? I guess, it needs that in order to calm or encourage our heart like a fist in our chest. Somehow it also relates to quotes, does not it? Have you ever tried to create your own grandiloquent quotation? I tried. As a result, I found. It can not mean my whole life but I have. You still have never tried to create yours, than create your own quotation from this moment.

Do not hurry up! Close your eyes.

Think about me, please! Daydream about me.

Please.. Write down your feelings about this.

I know it is very difficult to learn anything from these lines but my intention was to show that the only solution to every problem and confusion is to turn to Allah. True, sometimes we are lazy, sometimes we are stubborn. But if you keep writing such garbled lines on paper in your own hand, you will feel how much you need God. But try not to forget that God is always with us, he is with us.

Everyone looks sad and tired these days... SORRY.

Is it because people know what they live for or vice versa..!?

Is it because he doesn't know why he lives?

Garbled lines always have an end and it is called Allah. If you knew how happy you would be when you found the end of the tangled lines, your efforts to find it

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would be so intense." Everyone has their own lines, whether garbled or not and these stories were examples of lines in someone's life.

